

LEXICAL-SEMANTIC MEANINGS AND STYLISTIC FEATURES OF CAUSATIVE VERBS IN UZBEK LANGUAGE

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ABSTRACT

Causation is very important from social and communicative pragmatic point of view and is closely connected with the rapid development of cognitive linguistics. The modern linguistics is characterized by investigating the real task of the language in linguocognitive aspect. This process is focused on putting the cognitive semantics into first place. Investigating the view of the world from the cognitive point of view is taken place in every field of language layer, it is because is given opportunity to learn the essence of the language in every aspect and realizing the main role of the language. Moreover, the basic task of contemporary linguistics, mainly, cognitive linguistics is to investigate the role of human factor in language and realization of language facts.

KEYWORDS

Linguistics, causation, lexicology, semantics

1. INTRODUCTION

Despite the fact that causative conjunction has been actively discussed since the 1960s, linguistics has not yet given a universal definition of causative conjunction, showing the diversity of causative conjunctions in different languages. As M. Shibatani wrote 40 years ago, it is not easy to define causativeness, if we could give it a complete definition, then it would include the description of the grammatical features of all the constructions in which the causative index is realized.

Causativeness can rightfully be called one of the most mysterious, incompletely studied categories of language. The flowering of its study dates back to the second half of the 20th century, but until now its place in the system of many world languages has not been determined.

There are traditionally several directions in the study of the category of causation:

- 1) logical [N.D. Arutyunova, A.P. Komarov];
- 2) ontological [V.P. Nedyalkov, G.G. Silnitsky];
- 3) lexical and grammatical [M.V. Vsevolodova, T.A. Yashchenko, T.A. Qildibekova, N.P. Dushin and others];
- 4) functional-semantic [E.Ya. Gordon, G.A. Zolotova, T.A. Qildibekova, A.P. Chudinov, A.V. Filippov, S.V. Shustova, A.M. Amatov, Yu.V. Baklagova; N. Yu. Bessonov, I. B. Dolinina, U. Kordi, A. B. Uchish and others];
- 5) comparative typological [I.V. Kormushin, M.G. Simulov, S.E. Mrikaria, M.Kh. Alimova, S.K. Bevova and others];

- 6) semantic-syntactic [Sh. Bally, J. Lyons, L. Tenier, C. Fillmore, W.W. Bogdanov, I.A. Melchuk, M. Yu. Selivanova and others];
- 7) cognitive [J. Lakoff, A. Vejbitskaya, L. A. Furs, L. V. Kovaleva, N. Yu. Bessonov and others].

Note that all directions are conditional, since the study of causation is carried out in different directions. Approaches intersect, interact, complement each other, and enrich the entire theory of causation.

2. METHODS

The most discussed problems in the study of causative connection include: 1) questions of explaining the category of causation; 2) issues of determining causative verbs, criteria for their selection; 3) issues of determining the semantic-syntactic correlation of contact and remote causatives, factual and permissive adverbs, 4) the problem of causativeness as a visible derivative, study of causative adverbs; 5) means of expressing the category of causation in language, etc. We believe that the discussion of these and other problems on the material of the Uzbek language will serve as a source of completely new knowledge about causal connection and will help to fill and enrich the theory of linguistics. Let's take a look at the main trends in these issues.

The category of causation (Latin *causa* - cause) is related to the philosophical concepts of cause and effect. Causality is one of the main forms of interdependence and interdependence of the processes and phenomena of objective reality. It is known that causality has a universal meaning and exists in all forms of matter movement. Cause and effect reflect the relationships that actually exist in the world.

Causality is a philosophical category for defining the relationship of events in which one (called a cause) causes another (called an effect or action). All events and processes that occur in the world and in the mind are caused by other events and processes. The human psyche tends to distinguish causal relationships between individual facts of the surrounding world.

The French linguist S. Balli was one of the first to speak about causation: "Causation according to the coordination method corresponds to the formula: turn A into B, and according to the control method, causation Connection: Get A to B. The unusual nature of these inflections suggests that language often uses implicit means to express causal relationships.

I.A. As Melchuk notes, "the causative derivation is found in almost all languages of known language families, which is not surprising given the fundamental importance of causal relations in human life." This statement refers to the existence of causative derivatives in many languages, which is due to the fact that causal relations are specific and universal. T. Ergashev emphasizes that the category of causativeness expressed at the lexical and syntactic level is distinguished in many languages of the world.

The whole external and internal worlds are in interaction, one follows the other. Naturally, the system of interdependence of events is of great importance for a person. G.A. According to Zolotova, the linguistic image of the world is already "ready", can be presented in a static form or in the process of dynamic formation, with an explanation of some factors that caused the emergence of the situation. For example, the causative case - The breath of the wind opened our window a little - brings the development process forward and shows the cause that arose under the influence of another situation.

The speaker tries to determine the reasons that led to a certain result of actions. As it turns out, the speaker builds chains of interconnected events. It is these chains that are interpreted in the theory of causation as an expression of causal relations. In fact, the semantics of causation suggests a chain relationship between cause and effect. One connection is cause, the other is effect.

On the basis of the object actant of transitive verbs in the Uzbek language, a causative relationship also occurs. The causative relationship expressed according to the object actant is particularly important due to its unique feature, the fact that it is not an object of verification within the scope of case verbs in Turkology.

3. RESULTS

We know that causation represents a cause-and-effect relationship. In our opinion, this comes from a broad understanding of causation. In fact, the term causation means only "cause", "causal". Its semantic structure has no result meaning. But causation (reason) is directly connected with the result (or consequence) according to the logical connection. Because cause and effect are observed in a dialectical unity and connection. When we say cause, we mean the basis, source of the result perceived as a specific object by the sense organs, the subject, event, which is the means of its occurrence. In this respect, it (cause) is directly and logically connected with the result and includes the cause-and-effect act. So, this means that 1) the real connection of causation with a certain event, that is, if this word represents the source, cause of the occurrence of a certain event, 2) that the noted event does not happen without a reason as an act of result, cause and the result mean that there is a legal relationship between them, that the result is realized as a logical continuation of the cause.

V. I. Lenin says "The movement of the causal relationship is actually: the movement of matter...". The interaction of the movement of matter, its result, its manifestation in the fact of a certain language (speech) - the causative relationship is its reflection in the language. V. I. Lenin continues his opinion and emphasizes that "the causality that we usually understand is only a small particle of world-scale connection... it is not a subjective, but a particle of objectively real connection." So, the causal relationship exists as a real, objective fact. Causation and transitivity are formed from the relationship between objects, from the presence of the effector and affected objects, from their interaction. In the causative relationship, the object (patient) assumes the state under the influence of the agent (subject). An object in a certain state is realized as a result. Causation has subject, object and state components. The logical connection between them is necessary and constant for the causative relationship, such as the effect of the subject on the acquisition of the state of the object - the activity of the agent (subject) of causation (the presence of extralinguistic factors, factivity).

Both causation and transitivity are not typical for the semantic structure of state verbs in Uzbek. This, as mentioned above, is mainly due to the intransitive nature of the verbs.

The expression of causative relationship in language (speech) is its realization in linguistic units, and it (causative relationship) is expressed in speech in several ways.

Causative verbs in the Uzbek language mainly have the following forms of causative relation: 1. Semantic causative. 2. Morphological causative.

A characteristic feature of causative verbs with a semantic causative meaning is that they express a causative relationship in their meaning both when taken outside of speech (in language), without distribution, and in speech, with distribution. When the verbs with causative meaning are

taken as a language unit, the elements indicating the causative relationship in them are present in our mind, and they are stored in the form of a potential possibility. When verbs with causative meaning are observed as a speech unit in speech, they are characterized by the presence of direct organizers of the causative relationship, and the fact that they have a separate linguistic expression.

At the same time, in verbs with a semantic causative state (in general, in verbs with a semantic causative), regardless of the level of realization of the causative relation, it is always weaker and more passive compared to the morphological causative - in relation to the level of realization of the causative relation.

In the morphological causative, the cause-and-effect meaning that occurs under the influence of the causative ratio is concrete and clearly understood compared to the semantic causative. In the morphological causative, the activity of the causative relation is directly caused by the effect of the causative accretive formant, which we discussed in the discussion "Morphological causative".

It is observed in the category of morphological causative verb, in all lexical-semantic groups forming its semantic field. The morphological expression of the causative relation in case verbs has its own character. In the affixal formation of the causative relationship, the formants of the verb accretive are the main ones. They are of particular importance as a causative formant. Because the addition of the accusative-causative formant to case verbs, the "growth" of the phonetic structure of the verb logically and necessarily leads to a change in the semantics of the verb - the emergence of transitivity, causation.

The causative meaning of case verbs is mainly characterized by the addition of relative formants to intransitive case verbs. The addition of the accusative relative affix to intransitive verbs creates a cause-and-effect relationship in the meaning of the verb, the concept of "causation". By forming the accusative relative form of the verb, the agent of causation is formed. The direct effect of the causative-agent on the object is expressed in the causative formed by combining the accusative formant with intransitive verbs. So, it is the main, primary source of the changes observed in the patient (for example, the condition) and is the causative effect, action. According to this type of causation, factitive causation - active causation is considered.

Contact causative is the realization of the state of the verb in the object as a result of the direct effect of the causator. Distant causative semantic and morphological causative case verbs are often realized in speech as contact causative verbs. Because they have a unique potential for such realization. So, in the contact causative case, the change of state in the patient depends on the subject performing the action, that is, the first content act implements the second content act.

According to the results of observations, the appearance of the result in the semantics of the case verb with an accusative formant, its expression is seen in the creative role of the agent of causation realized by means of this formant. As mentioned, the agent is the cause of the patient's condition, the patient is directly affected by the agent. The fact that the object is under the influence of the actant of the agent is connected with the concept of action-activity. As a result of adding the accusative formant to the case verbs, they acquire the "meaning of activity", as noted by linguist H. Ne'matov, an active process occurs. It is distinguished by the fact that the verb has the meaning of activity and is realized in the accusative formant.

Therefore, the transition of state verbs to a speech unit with a specific accusative affix - a change in phonetic structure leads to a direct semantic change, and the transfer of the meaning of the state to the meaning of activity in speech. The meaning of activity is leading. But the meaning of the verb state is unique, it does not disappear completely, it is preserved, it becomes a potential

possibility. This process has attracted special attention as a concrete expression of the dialectical relationship between language and speech, as a morphological-semantic view.

The accusative form of case verbs clearly indicates that the executor of the case is the agent realized in this form of the word. In this case, the exact form of the ratio "... it is not intended who will perform the stated action". In addition, the agent actant is important because of its concreteness and semantic character. Accordingly, the causative relationship is clearly expressed in verbs with morphologic causative case. The elements of matter that entered the cause-effect relationship are fully embodied in the mind.

In the syntactic construction with a morphological causative, the semantic emphasis is mainly focused on the result state. Therefore, causation and patient status are imagined as one complex action and are expressed together in the construction.

It turned out that the intransitivity of state verbs in the Uzbek language is relative, and the addition of an accusative formant to them not only creates transitivity in the semantics of the state verb, but also creates a causative relationship. As mentioned, the subject, the source of causation is realized. Causative verbs formed from intransitive verbs have only factitive meaning.

4. DISCUSSION

The situation expressed in the morphological causative case verbs in the Uzbek language is often realized by a person, sometimes by an object. In this type of causative state verb sentences, the agent of causation and the implementer of the patient are mostly nouns and pronouns. It performs the function of possessive and passive complement. Causation agent and patient are syntactically realized in the sentence, sometimes they are not syntactically realized.

In the semantic group of action verbs, morphological causative verbs are divided into two types:

- 1) The agent of causation (mediated) is syntactically realized;
- 2) The agent of causation (mediated) is not syntactically realized.

State verbs with morphological causative meaning state verbs with semantic causative meaning more clearly and fully express a different causative relationship. The concrete, clear expression of the causative relationship in the verbs of the morphological causative state is due to the effect of the causative formant in the structure of the verbs of this state, its semantic possibility to clearly express the causative relation, the occurrence of the meaning of speech activity in the verbs of the morphological causative state, and this type of It is caused by concrete understanding of the agent of causation in case verbs with causative meaning.

If the causative meaning of semantically transitive verbs is considered a "fact" of language, the causative meaning of morphological transitive verbs is considered a "fact" of speech. Verbs with semantic and morphological causative meanings in the Uzbek language are notable for expressing contact causation in many cases, and distant causation in some cases. Verbs with semantic and morphological causative meaning indicate the richness of our language, its unique semantic possibilities, and the dialectical relationship between language and speech.

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